

Angelo Leogrande¹

The Reduction of NEETs in the Italian regions

The number of NEETs decreases in the macro-regions even if the value of the South is about 10 percentage points higher than the Italian average.

Istat calculates the amount of NEETs in the Italian regions. NEETs are defined as "[...] *Percentage of people aged 15-29 who are neither employed nor in an education or training path out of the total number of people aged 15-29.*"

The data was collected as part of the ISTAT-BES statistics referring to Sustainable Equitable Wellbeing. With reference to 2019, Sicily ranks first with a NEET percentage of 38%, followed by Calabria with an amount of 35.1%, and Campania with a value of 34.3%. In the middle of the table there are Lazio with a value of 20.7%, Liguria with a value of 17.7% and Piedmont with a value of 16.6%. Friuli-Venezia Giulia closes the ranking with an amount equal to 13.7%, followed by Veneto with an amount equal to 12.4% and Trentino Alto Adige with an amount equal to 11.1%. On average in the Italian regions in 2019 the value of NEETs was equal to 21.01%.

North. The number of NEETs in Northern Italy decreased in the period between 2015 and 2019 from an amount equal to 18.4 units up to a value of 14.5 units or equal to a change of -3.90 units equal to a value of -21.20%. In the passage between 2015 and 2016, the value of the NEET trend in Northern Italy went from a value of 18.4 units to a value of 16.9 units or equal to a change of -1.50 units equal to a value of -8.15%. Between 2016 and 2017 the value of the NEET trend went from a value of 16.9 units to a value of 16.7 units or equal to an amount of -0.20 units equal to -1, 18%. Between 2017 and 2018 the value of NEETs went from a value of 16.7 units to a value of 15.6 units or equal to a change of -1.10 units equal to a value of -6, 59%. In the transition between 2018 and 2019, the value of the NEET trend in Northern Italy decreased from a value of 15.6 units to a value of 14.5 units or equal to a value of -1.0 units equal at a value of -7.05%.

Center. In the passage between 2015 and 2019 the value of NEETs in the center decreased from an amount equal to 21.5 units up to a value equal to 18.1 units or a variation equal to a value of -3.40 units equal to a variation of -15.81%. Between 2015 and 2016 the value of NEETs decreased from a value equal to 21.5 units up to a value equal to 20.4 units or equal to a value of -1.10 units equal to a value of -5, 12%. In the transition between 2016 and 2017 the value of the NEET trend decreased from a value of 20.4 units to a value of 19.7 units or equal to a variation of -0.70 units equal to a value of -3.43%. In the transition between 2017 and 2018, the value of NEETs in the center went from a value of 19.7 units to a value of 19.6 units or equal to a variation of -0.10 units equal to a value of -0.51%. Between 2018 and 2019 the value of NEETs decreased from a value of 19.6 units to a value of 18.1 units or equal to a variation of -1.50 units equal to a value of -7, 65%.

Southern Italy. The number of NEETs in Southern Italy decreased between 2015 and 2019 from a value of 35.3% to a value of 33.00% or a reduction equal to a value of -2.30 units equal to a value of -6.52%. Between 2015 and 2016, the value of NEETs in the South went from a value of 35.3% to a value of 34.2% or equal to a reduction of -1.10 units equal to a value of -3.12%. Between 2016 and 2017 the value of the NEETs in the midday went from a value of 34.2% to a value of 34.4% or equal

¹ Ph.D., Assistant Professor of Economics at Lum University Giuseppe Degennaro, and researcher in Economics at LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Statale 100 km 18, Bari, Puglia, Italy. Email: leogrande.cultore@lum.it

to a variation of 0.20 units equal to a variation of 0, 58%. In the transition between 2017 and 2018, the value of NEETs in the South went from a value of 34.4% to a value of 33.8% or equal to a variation of -0.60 units equal to a variation of -1.74%. In the passage between 2018 and 2019 the value of NEETs went from a value equal to 33.8% up to a value equal to 33% or equal to a variation of -0.80 units equal to a value of -2, 37%. In the transition between 2015 and 2019 the value of NEETs in the South has decreased by a value equal to -2.30 units equal to a value of -6.52%.

Conclusions. The number of NEETs has decreased in the various Italian macro-regions. However, it should be considered that the value of NEETs in the South was on average equal to about 10.2 percentage points higher than the value of NEETs in Italy. The reduction in the number of NEETs requires economic policies of work and education capable of moving young people to intellectual, entrepreneurial, professional, political, and social commitment. Certainly, the low incomes and low remuneration of graduates offer poor incentives for the commitment of young people both in study and in work. To ensure that young people return to study and work, it is necessary to give dignity to study and work with an increase in income and the creation of ascending and merit-based professional paths.

Declarations

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